

The Nano-Age of Medicine: Effect of Silver Nanoparticle(in vitro) in increasing the efficacy and dose reduction of antibiotics against Multidrug resistant Acinetobacter baumannii from all ICU's in a tertiary care hospital

**1.Dr.Rajkumar Marimuthu , 2. Dr.Manonmoney. J , 3. Shruti.S
4. Dr. Leela K.V.**

1. Department of Microbiology, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu District, Tamil Nadu, India,603203
2. Department of Microbiology, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu District, Tamil Nadu, India, 603203
3. Department of Microbiology, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu District, Tamil Nadu, India, 603203
4. Department of Microbiology, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu District, Tamil Nadu, India, 603203

*Correspondence: - **Dr.Rajkumar Marimuthu**

Abstract:**Background:**

Acinetobacter baumannii is a widespread pathogen and a leading cause of healthcare-associated infections, often affecting the respiratory tract, urinary tract, bloodstream, and surgical sites. Its rapid development of resistance to major antibiotic groups has made it a critical concern. Nanotechnology offers a novel approach to counteract these resistant microbes.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective study involved 200 *A. baumannii* isolates, including multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains, from ICU patients. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were synthesized using chemical reduction, characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, and tested for antimicrobial activity via MIC determination.

Results:

The prevalence of MDR *A. baumannii* was 16%, with male patients (59.4%) and those over 60 years old (46.9%) being most affected. Improvement was noted in 37.5% of patients. Resistance was observed against multiple antibiotics, including Cefotaxime, Gentamicin, Ciprofloxacin, and Meropenem. Combining antibiotics with AgNPs significantly reduced the MIC, indicating enhanced antimicrobial activity.

Conclusion:

AgNPs demonstrate potential to enhance antimicrobial activity, suggesting a promising

therapeutic avenue for MDR *A. baumannii* infections. Implementing strict antimicrobial stewardship and continued surveillance is essential to curb the spread of resistant strains.

Keywords: Multidrug Resistance, Silver Nanoparticles, Nanotechnology, Antimicrobial Activity.

INTRODUCTION:

Acinetobacter baumannii is a gram-negative opportunistic pathogen, commonly associated with life-threatening nosocomial infections and outbreaks, particularly in critical care settings [1]. Estimates of mortality rates among patients with *A. baumannii* infections have ranged from 26.0% to 55.7%, with estimated attributable mortality rates between 8.4% and 36.5%. While bacteremia and pneumonia are the most severe infections caused by *A. baumannii*, this organism can cause a variety of other serious infections including urinary tract infections, skin and soft tissue infections, wound infections, osteomyelitis, and meningitis [2]. The emergence of *A. baumannii* as a successful nosocomial pathogen is generally attributed to its capacity to exhibit multidrug resistance through more than one type of mechanism which has made it even more difficult to treat the infection [6]. The phenomenon of multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens has increasingly become a serious concern to both nosocomial and community-acquired infections [7]. The high prevalence of MDRAB and/or CRAB strains presents a real challenge for clinical treatment, as resistance is associated with inappropriate initial therapy and worse outcomes for patients with *A. baumannii* infection, including higher mortality. They have become highly resistant to a broad spectrum of antibiotics like penicillin, third-generation cephalosporins, carboxypenicillins, carbapenems. Most strains are resistant to fluoroquinolones as well [8,9].

Nanotechnology is a new strategy in the antimicrobial field that is being developed to put an end to resistant microbes. In general, nanoparticle forms of such metals as platinum, silver, copper, and gold have antimicrobial activities against various pathogenic bacteria and fungi. Specifically, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have promising applications in nanotechnology and nanomedicine and have been approved for their bactericidal activity against broad spectrum bacterial infections as well as for their fungicide effects [10,11]. Silver has been used since antiquity for its bactericidal properties, and with the advent of technology, nanostructures with this metal have shown an improvement in their activity due to their highly reactive multifaceted structure. Silver ions are highly reactive and bind to bacterial proteins, causing structural changes in the cell wall and membrane. Furthermore, they denature the DNA and ribosomal proteins that synthesize substances essential for the metabolism of microorganisms. These effects are potentiated by the reactive oxygen species generated by the silver nanoparticles, which justifies its probable deleterious mechanism [13]. Keeping these above facts in view, the present research work has been aimed to analyze the prevalence, risk factors, clinical outcome of MDR *Acinetobacter baumannii* . and the antimicrobial potential of AgNPs against MDR *A. baumannii*.

MATERIALS & METHODS :

The present prospective study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu and from the Institute Ethical Committee for Human Studies, ethical

approval (SRMIEC-ST1122229) was acquired. A total of 200 known *A. baumannii* isolates including Multidrug resistant *A. baumannii* from various clinical specimens, such as tissue, swabs from wounds, pus, sputum, and urine from the ICU patients were included. All other organisms isolated and reported other than *A. baumannii* from the ICU were excluded.

All Bacterial isolates were identified on the basis of routine microbiological techniques by performing direct Gram staining and were streaked on nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, and Blood agar. However, the urine sample was streaked only on UTI Chrom agar and Blood agar. Following an 18–24-hour incubation period, the colonies' morphology was studied, and it was determined that they were non-hemolytic, grey-colored colonies on Nutrient agar, blood agar and MacConkey agar.

The bacterial colonies were subjected to the confirmed *A. baumannii* by VITEK 2 system (Biomérieux, France) using VITEK® 2 GN ID Card and VITEK® 2 GP ID Card (according to the manufacturer's instructions).

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test:

Antibiotic susceptibility was assessed using the VITEK 2 system with the AST-GN48 TEST KIT (Biomérieux, France) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The microdilution assay served as the reference method, following CLSI guidelines (M07 Ed12, 2024). Antimicrobial agents tested included cefepime, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, imipenem, levofloxacin, meropenem, piperacillin, ticarcillin, tobramycin, co-trimoxazole, and tetracycline, with concentration ranges from 512 to 0.25 µg/ml depending on the antibiotic.

Results from the VITEK 2 system were categorized as correct identification, low-level discrimination, no identification, or misidentification. Essential agreement (EA), defined as MICs within 1 twofold dilution, was used to compare methods.

Synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs)

AgNPs (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared via chemical reduction of silver nitrate in presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) as a stabilizer according to Zielińska, A et al [16]. The obtained samples were stirred, forming AgNPs. AgNPs formation was proved by Ultraviolet–visible spectral analysis. The absorbance spectra were determined using UV spectroscopy at a wavelength of 300–700 nm. The obtained NPs were characterized using transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy [17,18].

Figure 1:Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

Figure 2 :Characterization by UV-Vis Spectrophotometry

FE-SEM Analysis

NPs were assessed by FE-SEM for size, surface morphology, and homogeneity. With this method, it was possible to get information on the NPs' size and shape in addition to quantitative and qualitative data. The diameter of the nanoscale-synthesised particles was measured using ImageJ software (Java 1.8.0, Gaithersburg, MD, USA). The bulk of the AgNPs are spherical in form, smooth on the surface and exhibiting particle agglomeration and aggregation. The structures ranged in size from 84.67 nm to 78.80 nm

Figure 3:SEM analysis of AgNp coating with different antibiotics

Loading of Antibiotics with silver nanoparticles:

Ciprofloxacin onto silver nanoparticles

For the purpose of enhancing the interaction between the antibiotic and the AgNPs, 100 mL of the synthesised AgNPs were combined with 0.001 M aqueous solution of CIP and the mixture was continuously stirred under ultra-sonication.

Cefotaxime onto silver nanoparticles

The preparation of CTX@AgNPs involved mixing 100 mL of the synthesised AgNPs with 0.001 M aqueous solution of CTX while continuously swirling under ultra-sonication to improve the interaction between the antibiotic and the AgNPs.

Gentamycin onto silver nanoparticles

To improve the interaction between the antibiotic and the AgNPs, 0.001 M aqueous solution of GEN was added to 100 mL of the synthesised AgNPs and continuously stirred under ultra-sonication. This process produced GEN@AgNPs.

Meropenem onto silver nanoparticles

To increase the interaction between the antibiotic and the AgNPs, 0.001 M aqueous solution of MRP was added to 100 mL of the synthesised AgNPs while being continuously stirred under ultra-sonication. This process produced MRP@AgNPs.

Azithromycin onto silver nanoparticles

To improve the interaction between the antibiotic and the AgNPs, 0.001 M aqueous solution of AZM was added to 100 mL of the synthesised AgNPs and continuously stirred under ultra-sonication. This process produced AZM@AgNPs.

Amoxicillin Clavulanate onto silver nanoparticles

To improve the interaction between the antibiotic and the AgNPs, 0.001 M aqueous solution of AMC was added to 100 mL of the synthesised AgNPs and continuously stirred under ultra-sonication. This process produced AMC @AgNPs.

Figure 4: Antibiotics with silver nanoparticles

Results:

The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) data for 32 MDR *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates showed high resistance to Cefotaxime (MIC \geq 64 μ g for 16 isolates), Gentamicin (MIC \geq 64 μ g for 14 isolates), and Azithromycin (MIC \geq 64 μ g for 21 isolates). Meropenem exhibited comparatively lower resistance, with MIC \leq 8 μ g for most isolates. Combining antibiotics with AgNPs significantly reduced MIC values. Cefotaxime+AgNPs decreased MIC to as low as 1 μ g in 6 isolates. Gentamicin+AgNPs reduced MIC to 1 μ g in 8 isolates, while Meropenem+AgNPs achieved the lowest MIC of 0.12 μ g in 6 isolates. Azithromycin+AgNPs reduced MIC to 4 μ g in 18 isolates, and Amoxicillin-clavulanate+AgNPs lowered MIC to 1 μ g in 4 isolates. These combinations demonstrated enhanced antimicrobial activity, suggesting a synergistic effect that could lower required antibiotic doses and mitigate side effects.

Table 1: MIC of Cefotaxime among MDR *A. baumannii* isolates by Microbroth dilution (n-32)

	MIC of Cefotaxime						
	64 μ g	32 μ g	16 μ g	8 μ g	4 μ g	2 μ g	1 μ g
MIC of Cefotaxime against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	14	8	6	4	-	-	-
MIC of Cefotaxime + AgNPs against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	-	-	2	7	10	7	6

The MIC of Cefotaxime against MDR *A. baumannii* revealed that among 32 isolates, 14 exhibited the highest MIC of 64 μ g, followed by 8 isolates with a MIC of 32 μ g, 6 isolates with a MIC of 16 μ g, and 4 isolates with a MIC of 2 μ g. However, when combined with AgNPs, there was a notable reduction in the MIC of MDR isolates. Specifically, 10 isolates showed a MIC of 4 μ g, 7 isolates had a MIC of 8 μ g, 7 isolates had a MIC of 2 μ g, and 6 isolates had a MIC of 1 μ g.

Table 2: MIC of Gentamycin among MDR *A. baumannii* isolates by Microbroth dilution (n-32)

	MIC of Gentamycin						
	64 μ g	32 μ g	16 μ g	8 μ g	4 μ g	2 μ g	1 μ g
MIC of Gentamycin against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	14	11	2	5	-	-	-
MIC of Gentamycin + AgNPs against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	-	-	-	4	16	4	8

The MIC of Gentamicin against MDR *A. baumannii* indicated that among 32 isolates, 14 demonstrated the highest MIC of 64 μ g, followed by 11 isolates with a MIC of 32 μ g, 2 isolates with a MIC of 16 μ g, and 5 isolates with a MIC of 8 μ g. However, when combined with AgNPs, there was a significant reduction in the MIC of MDR isolates. Specifically, 16 isolates showed a MIC of 4 μ g, 8 isolates had a MIC of 1 μ g, 4 isolates had a MIC of 8 μ g, and 4 isolates had a MIC of 2 μ g.

Table 3: MIC of Ciprofloxacin among MDR *A. baumannii* isolates by Microbroth dilution (n-32)

	MIC of Ciprofloxacin						
	2 μ g	1 μ g	0.8 μ g	0.6 μ g	0.4 μ g	0.2 μ g	0.1 μ g
MIC of Ciprofloxacin against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	9	15	3	5	-	-	-
MIC of Ciprofloxacin + AgNPs against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	-	5	13	1	10	3	-

The MIC of Ciprofloxacin against MDR *A. baumannii* indicated that among 32 isolates, 15 demonstrated a MIC of 1 μ g, followed by 9 isolates with a MIC of 2 μ g, 5 isolates with a MIC of 0.6 μ g, and 3 isolates with a MIC of 0.8 μ g. However, when combined with AgNPs, there was a significant reduction in the MIC of MDR isolates. Specifically, 13 isolates showed a MIC of 0.8 μ g, 10 isolates had a MIC of 0.4 μ g, 5 isolates had a MIC of 1 μ g, 3 isolates had a MIC of 0.2 μ g, and 1 isolate had a MIC of 0.6 μ g.

	MIC of Meropenem						
	8 μ g	4 μ g	2 μ g	1 μ g	0.5 μ g	0.25 μ g	0.12 μ g
MIC of Meropenem against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	13	10	7	2	-	-	-
MIC of Meropenem + AgNPs against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	-	-	-	11	10	5	6

Table 4: MIC of Meropenem among MDR *A. baumannii* isolates by Microbroth dilution (n-32)

The MIC of Meropenem against MDR *A. baumannii* revealed that among 32 isolates, 13 demonstrated a MIC of 8 μ g, followed by 10 isolates with a MIC of 4 μ g, 7 isolates with a MIC of 2 μ g, and 2 isolates with a MIC of 1 μ g. However, when combined with AgNPs, there was a significant reduction in the MIC of MDR isolates. Specifically, 11 isolates showed a MIC of 1 μ g, 10 isolates had a MIC of 0.5 μ g, 6 isolates had a MIC of 0.12 μ g, and 5 isolates had a MIC of 0.25 μ g.

	MIC of Azithromycin						
	64 μ g	32μg	16μ g	8 μg	4μg	2μg	1 μg
MIC of Azithromycin against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	21	5	2	4	-	-	-
MIC of Azithromycin + AgNPs against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	-	-	2	6	18	3	3

Table 5: MIC of Azithromycin among MDR *A. baumannii* isolates by Microbroth dilution (n-32)

The MIC of Azithromycin against MDR *A. baumannii* indicated that among 32 isolates, 21 demonstrated the highest MIC of 64 μg, followed by 5 isolates with a MIC of 32 μg, 4 isolates with a MIC of 8 μg, and 2 isolates with a MIC of 16 μg. However, when combined with AgNPs, there was a notable reduction in the MIC of MDR isolates. Specifically, 18 isolates showed a MIC of 4 μg, 6 isolates had a MIC of 8 μg, 3 isolates had a MIC of 2 μg, 2 isolates had a MIC of 2 μg, and 2 isolate had a MIC of 16 μg.

Table 6: MIC of Amoxicillin with clavulanic acid among MDR *A. baumannii* isolates by Microbroth dilution (n-32)

	MIC of Amoxicillin with clavulanic acid						
	64 μg	32μg	16μg	8 μg	4μg	2μg	1 μg
MIC of Amoxicillin with clavulanic acid against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	11	14	6	1	-	-	-
MIC of Amoxicillin with clavulanic acid + AgNPs against MDR <i>A. baumannii</i> (n-32)	-	-	9	11	3	5	4

The MIC of Amoxicillin with clavulanic acid against MDR *A. baumannii* indicated that among 32 isolates, 14 demonstrated a MIC of 32 μg, followed by 11 isolates with a MIC of 64 μg, 6 isolates with a MIC of 16 μg, and 1 isolate with a MIC of 8 μg. However, when combined with AgNPs, there was a significant reduction in the MIC of MDR isolates. Specifically, 11 isolates showed a MIC of 8 μg, 9 isolates had a MIC of 16 μg, 5 isolates had a MIC of 2 μg, 4 isolates had a MIC of 1 μg, and 3 isolates had a MIC of 4 μg.

Combining antibiotics with AgNPs significantly reduced MIC values. These combinations demonstrated enhanced antimicrobial activity, suggesting a synergistic effect that could lower required antibiotic doses and mitigate side effects.

DISCUSSION:

Multidrug-resistant (MDR) *Acinetobacter baumannii* is a significant global healthcare challenge, particularly in ICU settings, where it frequently causes respiratory, urinary tract, wound, and bloodstream infections. In this study, 16% of isolates were MDR, lower than rates reported by Shrestha et al. (96%) and Purohit M et al. (87%), highlighting regional variations due to antimicrobial stewardship and infection control measures. Male patients (59.4%) and those aged ≥ 60 years (53.1%) showed a higher prevalence, consistent with findings by Sukanya S et al., while most MDR isolates were from tracheal aspirates (50%) and sputum (30%). Chronic comorbidities, prior antibiotic use (87.5%), and diabetes (65.6%) were significant predictors of morbidity and mortality, aligning with Liu et al. and Jang et al., who emphasized the role of underlying conditions in outcomes. The study demonstrated a 15.6% mortality rate among MDR *A. baumannii* patients, with older age, comorbidities, and invasive device use as key risk factors. However, a 37.5% improvement rate was observed, underscoring the importance of prompt and appropriate antimicrobial therapy and infection control measures. Resistance was noted against several antibiotics, including Cefotaxime, Gentamicin, and Meropenem. Combining antibiotics with AgNPs significantly reduced MICs, suggesting a synergistic effect. These findings align with studies by Łysakowska et al. and Kaikan F et al., highlighting AgNPs as promising adjuvants to enhance antibiotic efficacy while potentially reducing toxicity and side effects. This innovative approach may improve treatment outcomes for MDR *A. baumannii* infections.

CONCLUSION:

According to the current investigation, 16% of the isolates were found to be MDR *A. baumannii*, pointing to a worrying increase in infections at our institution. A reduction in needless admissions to critical care units, shorter hospital stays, early comorbidity stabilisation and improved intubation techniques may all lead to better results. Our research demonstrated the potential value of AgNPs as a supplemental treatment to

fight antibiotic resistance and enhance the prognosis of MDR infection patients AgNPs have been shown to significantly increase antimicrobial activity, which suggests a viable way to improve the novel therapeutic approach for MDR *A. baumannii* infections. Strict antimicrobial stewardship protocols and ongoing surveillance are essential for preventing the spread of MDR *A. baumannii*.

REFERENCES:

1. Baleivanualala SC, Isaia L, Devi SV, et al. Molecular and clinical epidemiology of carbapenem resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* ST2 in Oceania: a multicountry cohort study. *Lancet Reg Health West Pac*. 2023;40:100896. Published 2023 Sep 22. doi:10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100896.
2. Falagas ME, Rafailidis PI. 2007. Attributable mortality of *Acinetobacter baumannii*: no longer a controversial issue. *Crit Care* 11:134.
3. A. AA, V. K. A. Prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility of acinetobacter in a tertiary care hospital in Chennai, India. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*. Published online January 15, 2021:35-40. doi:10.22159/ijcpr.2021v13i1.40803.
4. Islahi S, Ahmad F, Khare V, Yaqoob S, Shukla P, Singh Y. Incidence and risk factors associated with *Acinetobacter* species infection in hospitalised patients in a tertiary care hospital in North-India. *J Comm Dis*. 2015;46(3):10–12.
5. Singh, S., Singh, A. K., Singh, M. K., Jain, M., & Lahiri, K. K. Prevalence and antibiogram of *Acinetobacter baumannii* from various clinical samples in a tertiary care hospital. 2022; 13(4):967-976.

6. Kumkar SN, Kamble EE, Chavan NS, Dhotre DP, Pardesi KR. Diversity of resistant determinants, virulence factors, and mobile genetic elements in *Acinetobacter baumannii* from India: A comprehensive in silico genome analysis. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2022;12:997897. doi:10.3389/fcimb.2022.997897
7. Pratiwi DIN, Danesihdewi A. The prevalence of carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Ulin General Hospital Banjarmasin. *Eurasia J Biosci*. 2020;14:7787-7792.
8. Appaneal HJ, Lopes VV, LaPlante KL, Caffrey AR. Treatment, Clinical Outcomes, and Predictors of Mortality among a National Cohort of Admitted Patients with *Acinetobacter baumannii* Infection. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2022;66(3):e0197521. doi:10.1128/AAC.01975-21
9. Lemos EV, de la Hoz FP, Einarson TR, et al. Carbapenem resistance and mortality in patients with *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2014;20(5):416-423. doi:10.1111/1469-0691.12363.
10. L. Dent, D.R. Marshall, S. Pratap, R.B. Hulette, Multidrug resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii*: a descriptive study in a city hospital, *BMC Infect Dis*. 10 (2010) 196,

11. Shaker MA, Shaaban MI. Synthesis of silver nanoparticles with antimicrobial and anti-adherence activities against multidrug-resistant isolates from *Acinetobacter baumannii*. *J Taibah Univ Med Sci*. 2017;12(4):291-297. Published 2017 Apr 24. doi:10.1016/j.jtumed.2017.02.008
12. Rai M.K., Deshmukh S.D., Ingle A.P., Gade A.K. Silver nanoparticles: the powerful nanoweapon against multidrug-resistant bacteria. *J Appl Microbiol*. 2012;112:841–852.
13. Camargo LO, Fontoura I, Veriato TS, Raniero L, Castilho ML. Antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles functionalized with amikacin applied against multidrug-resistant acinetobacter baumannii. *Am J Infect Control*. 2023;51(8):871-878. doi:10.1016/j.ajic.2022.12.009
14. M07 ED12: Methods for dilution antimicrobial susceptibility tests for bacteria that grow aerobically, 12th edition. Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute. Accessed August 10, 2024.
15. Joyanes P, del Carmen Conejo M, Martínez-Martínez L, Perea EJ. Evaluation of the VITEK 2 system for the identification and susceptibility testing of three species of nonfermenting gram-negative rods frequently isolated from clinical samples. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2001;39(9):3247-3253. doi:10.1128/JCM.39.9.3247-3253.2001
16. Zielińska, A., Skwarek, E., Zaleska, A., Gazda, M. & Hupka, J. Preparation of silver nanoparticles with controlled particle size. *Procedia Chem*. 1, 1560–1566 (2009).
17. Jyoti, K., Baunthiyal, M. & Singh, A. Characterization of silver nanoparticles synthesized using *Urtica dioica* Linn. leaves and their synergistic effects with antibiotics. *J. Radiat. Res. Appl. Sci*. 9, 217–227 (2016).
18. Al-Dhabi, N. A., Ghilan, A.-K.M., Arasu, M. V. & Duraipandiyani, V. Green biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles produced from marine *Streptomyces* sp Al-Dhabi-89 and their potential applications against wound infection and drug resistant clinical pathogens. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B Biol*. 189, 176–184 (2018).

19. Sharma RK, Mamoria VP. A Prospective Study on Prevalence and Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Clinical Samples obtained from patients admitted in Various Wards and Intensive Care Units. *J Mahatma Gandhi Univ Med Sci Tech* 2017;2(3):122-127.
20. J.A. Karlowsky et al., Surveillance for antimicrobial susceptibility among clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacterbaumannii* from hospitalized patients in the United States, 1998 to 2001, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 47 (2003) 1681–1688.
21. Sileem AE, Said AM, Meleha MS. *Acinetobacter baumannii* in ICU patients: A prospective study highlighting their incidence, antibiotic sensitivity pattern and impact on ICU stay and mortality. *Egyptian Journal of Chest Diseases and Tuberculosis.* 2017;66(4):693-698. doi:10.1016/j.ejcdt.2017.01.003
22. Kim YJ, Kim SI, Hong KW, Kim YR, Park YJ, Kang MW. Risk factors for mortality in patients with carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* bacteremia: impact of appropriate antimicrobial therapy. *J Korean Med Sci* 2012 May;27(5): 471-475.
23. Shrestha S, Tada T, Shrestha B, et al. Phenotypic characterization of multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* with special reference to metallo- β -lactamase production from the hospitalized patients in a tertiary care hospital in Nepal. *JIOM.* 2015;37(3):3–10
24. Mishra SK, Rijal BP, Pokhrel BM. Emerging threat of multidrug resistant bugs – *acinetobacter calcoaceticus baumannii* complex and Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *BMC Res Notes.* 2013;6(1):1. doi: 10.1186/1756-0500-6-98
25. Purohit M, Mendiratta DK, Deotale VS, Madhan M, Manoharan A, Narang P. Detection of metallo-b-lactamases producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* using microbiological assay, disc synergy test and PCR. *Indian J Med Microbiol* 2012 Oct-Dec;30(4):456-461

26. Kamali M, Manshouri S, Bagheri Y, et al. Prevalence and antibiotic resistance of *Acinetobacter baumannii* among patients in postcardiac surgery intensive care units of Rajaei Hospital, Tehran. *Med J Islam Repub Iran*. 2020;34:4. Published 2020 Feb 11. doi:10.34171/mjiri.34.4
27. Sudhaharan Sukanya, Vemu Lakshmi, Kanne Padmaja. Prevalence of multidrug resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* in clinical samples in a tertiary care hospital *Int J Infect Control* 2014, v11:i3 doi: 10.3396/IJIC.v11i3.023.15.
28. Jean Uwingabiye et al. *Acinetobacter* infections prevalence and frequency of the antibiotics resistance: comparative study of intensive care units versus other hospital units. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2016;23:191. [doi: 10.11604/pamj.2016.23.191.7915]
29. Sharma RK, Mamoria VP. A Prospective Study on Prevalence and Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Clinical Samples obtained from Patients admitted in Various Wards and Intensive Care Units. *J Mahatma Gandhi Univ Med Sci Tech* 2017;2(3):122-127.
30. Jang, T.N.; Lee, S.H.; Huang, C.H.; Lee, C.L.; Chen, W.Y. Risk factors and impact of nosocomial *Acinetobacter baumannii* bloodstream infections in the adult intensive care unit: A case-control study. *J. Hosp. Infect.* 2009, 73, 143–150
31. Kanafani, Z.A., Zahreddine, N., Tayyar, R. et al. Multi-drug resistant *Acinetobacter* species: a seven-year experience from a tertiary care center in Lebanon. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control* 7, 9 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-017-0297-6>
32. Salam MA, Al-Amin MY, Salam MT, Pawar JS, Akhter N, Rabaan AA, Alqumber MAA. Antimicrobial Resistance: A Growing Serious Threat for Global Public Health. *Healthcare*. 2023; 11(13):1946. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11131946>
33. Łysakowska ME, Ciebiada-Adamiec A, Klimek L, Sienkiewicz M. The activity of silver nanoparticles (Axonnite) on clinical and environmental strains of *Acinetobacter* spp. *Burns*. 2015;41(2):364–371.

34. Shokrollahi B, Bafroee AST, Saleh T. Effect of Zinc Oxide nanoparticles on loaded antibiotics against Multidrug-Resistant *Acinetobacter* spp. *Avicenna J Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2021;8(2):51–6.
35. Kakian F, Arasteh N, Mirzaei E, Motamedifar M. Study of MIC of silver and zinc oxide nanoparticles, strong and cost-effective antibacterial against biofilm-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Shiraz, Southwest of Iran. *BMC Infect Dis*. 2024;24(1):593. Published 2024 Jun 17. doi:10.1186/s12879-024-09471-1
36. Wang N, Luo J, Deng F, Huang Y, Zhou H. Antibiotic Combination Therapy: A Strategy to Overcome Bacterial Resistance to Aminoglycoside Antibiotics. *Front Pharmacol*. 2022;13:839808. Published 2022 Feb 23. doi:10.3389/fphar.2022.839808